

Appendix

A1

IR, MP, BDD, RM and MC conducted the in-depth interviews with stakeholders (stage 2, figure 2).

IR, and MP administered the SWOT/SOr to stakeholders (stage 4, figure 2).

At the time of the study, MP, BDD, RM and MC were PhD, IR was MSc. RM and MC were full professors, MP and BDD were associate professors, and IR was a PhD student.

All the researchers were female, except for MP, who was male.

BDD, MP, and IR had previous experiences in conducting focus groups, and trained with the other ones about the specific subject of the study.

Researcher shortly introduced themselves and the project to the participant when they asked for their availability.

A2

Data were collected at workplaces and only participants and researchers were present.

Three researchers coded the data, and the main results are in the main text.

Data were analysed in Microsoft Excel.